

ABSTRACT

Background: People who have suffered falls are at greater risk of falling again. We study the characteristics of falls leading to hip fracture in people with a history of recurrent falls, comparing them with those of people with a history of sporadic falling.

Materials and methods: Analysis of the characteristics of a sample of 1225 patients consecutively admitted to six hospitals because of a hip fracture secondary to a fall (index fall) - index fall characteristics (location, time and the possible cause of the fall: intrinsic, extrinsic or combined risk factors) were also determined. Patients with a history of three or more falls (recurrent fallers) in the year prior to the index fall were identified as high-risk fallers; those with less than three falls were considered to be sporadic fallers.

Results: The mean number of falls in the year prior to the index fall was 1.7+/- 6.5; 227 patients (22%) had experienced three or more falls within that period. Most index falls (880, 71.8%) took place at the patient's home, 232 (18.95%) in the street and 113 (9.2%) elsewhere; most (892, 72.9%) took place during daytime. Multiple stepwise logistic regression analysis showed that recurrent fallers were characterized by poorer baseline independence for activities of the daily living, a prior diagnosis of dementia, greater use of prescription drugs and a greater use of neuroleptics. For frequent fallers, the index fall was more often associated with an intrinsic factor than for sporadic fallers.

Conclusions: A significant percentage of patients experiencing a fall followed by hip fracture have a history of recurrent falling in the year prior to a fall-related hip fracture. Poorer functional and cognitive status, polypharmacy and the use of neuroleptics are more prevalent in this subgroup of patients, and intrinsic factors as a cause of the fall are more common in this group. Whether these circumstances associated with recurrent falling are responsible for this higher prevalence of intrinsic, non-accidental falls should be addressed prospectively in order to implement preventive strategies.